

Assessing the value of data for prediction policies: The case of antibiotic prescribing

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ABSTRACT

We quantify the value of data for the prediction policy problem of reducing antibiotic prescribing to curb antibiotic resistance. Using varying combinations of administrative data, we evaluate machine learning predictions for diagnosing bacterial urinary tract infections and the outcomes of prescription rules based on these predictions. Simple patient demographics improve prediction quality substantially but larger reductions in prescribing can be achieved by making use of rich health data. Our results suggest decreasing returns to data for prediction quality and increasing returns for policy outcomes. Hence, data needs for prediction policy problems must be assessed based on the policy objective and not only on prediction quality.

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1. Introduction

The increasing digitization of patient data has led to a surge of case studies on how data may improve efficiency in health care (Obermeyer and Emanuel, 2016; Ribers and Ullrich, 2022; Yelin et al., 2019; Hastings et al., 2020). However, accessing individualized data has significant operative and social costs (Price and Cohen, 2019). Data collection, storage, and ownership are fragmented across providers, insurance systems, and regional administrations (Zeltzer et al., 2019). To balance costs and potential benefits of data combination, it is important to quantify the value added from combining different data sources.

We quantify the potential value of combined data for improving antibiotic prescribing to curb antibiotic resistance through the lens of a prediction policy problem (Kleinberg et al., 2015; Agrawal et al., 2018). We link administrative data with laboratory diagnostic data from Denmark to evaluate the predictions of an algorithm trained to identify bacterial urinary tract infections in primary care. The decision to prescribe an antibiotic reduces to a prediction problem because the medical benefits and costs of treatment are known once a bacterial condition is diagnosed, but a definitive laboratory diagnostic takes time, an average of

three days in our setting. Observing the true bacterial outcome in the laboratory data, we retrospectively evaluate improvements in the algorithm's predictions by their potential to target antibiotic prescriptions compared to physicians' initial decisions.

The need for solutions to curb antibiotic resistance is urgent. In the US alone, antibiotic-resistant infections result in 23,000 deaths, \$20 billion in direct healthcare costs, and \$35 billion in lost productivity every year (CDC, 2013). Antibiotic use in primary care accounts for the bulk of human antibiotic consumption, which is regarded as the main driver of antibiotic resistance (Llor and Bjerrum, 2014; Adda, 2020). We consider antibiotic use in 72,685 initial primary care visits for suspected urinary tract infections over a three-year period. We focus on consultations in which a laboratory diagnostic was used. These cases provide a high-quality ground truth for counterfactual evaluations but imply that our results may not directly extend to situations without laboratory testing.

We find that, for prediction quality, using patient age and gender achieves an area under the receiver operating curve (AUC) of 0.752 compared to 0.686 based on the most basic set of predictors. The reduction in antibiotic use can be increased from 0.66 to 4.96 percent. Adding rich data on patients' medical histories in contrast improves prediction quality only from an AUC of 0.756 to 0.783 but increases the reduction in antibiotic use from 5.33 to 9.32 percent. Due to their high dimensionality, these data may provide new information for antibiotic prescription decisions while physicians likely know a patient's age and gender. The relative improvements in prediction quality show decreasing returns in the scope of data but increasing returns for policy outcomes.

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In retrospective analyses, the existing literature either bases assessments of the value of linking data on prediction quality (Zeltzer et al., 2019; Eisenberg et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Bonde et al., 2021) or does not consider the incremental value of data (Yelin et al., 2019; Hastings et al., 2020). Few exceptions develop an algorithm to evaluate its application in clinical practice (Razavian et al., 2020; Mišić et al., 2021). Ribers and Ullrich (2020, 2022) find that combining machine learning and physician expertise may improve antibiotic prescribing. For a similar policy, we retrospectively quantify the potential, incremental value of administrative data for prediction quality and decision outcomes. Our results document that the value of data depends on the objective function and the information human decision makers hold.

2. Empirical analysis

2.1. Machine learning prediction

We consider a binary prediction problem for positive and negative urine culture test results produced by microbiological laboratories. A test result is positive when significant bacteria are found in a sample, resulting in a bacterial urinary tract infection diagnosis (Hooton, 1990). We construct a classification model that predicts test results using the Extreme Gradient Boosting algorithm (XGBoost) (Friedman, 2001; Chen and Guestrin, 2016). The XGBoost algorithm builds an ensemble of classification trees and is well-suited for high-dimensional structured data.

For each data combination, we optimize the learning rate, number of boosting rounds, and tree depth as hyperparameters, using the AUC as optimization criterion. We account for time dependency in our data by splitting the first year we observe, 2010, into hyperparameter evaluation partitions consisting of the months October, November, and December. We tune on these partitions using all prior observations in 2010 as training partitions. Given hyperparameters, we construct risk predictions month-by-month for 24 monthly out-of-sample evaluation partitions, from January 2011 to December 2012, using the twelve months prior to each partition as training data. We evaluate prediction quality by AUC and compute confidence intervals by re-sampling 1,000 bootstrap samples with replacement from the evaluation data.

2.2. Prediction policy problem

We consider a policy maker's payoff from prescription decisions at initial consultations where a urine sample is collected from patients. Antibiotics can be prescribed before receiving laboratory test results, but this practice risks prescribing to patients without a bacterial infection while promoting resistance. Alternatively, prescriptions can be delayed until the test result is known, 3.1 days on average in our sample.

A prescription decision $d \in \{0, 1\}$ resolves the trade-off between a patient's sickness cost α from delayed prescribing and the social cost of prescribing β from promoting resistance. While the social cost of prescribing is incurred for every antibiotic prescribed, the cost of waiting is only incurred if the patient suffers from a bacterial infection. The payoff from an individual patient's initial consultation can be written as

$$\pi(d; y) = -\alpha y(1 - d) - \beta d, \quad (1)$$

where y is an indicator for whether the patient has a bacterial infection, that is, $y = 1$ if the test outcome is positive and zero otherwise. We denote a decision rule that generates prescription decisions as a function of machine learning predictions by δ . Observed physician decisions are denoted by δ^j . The change

in payoffs induced by counterfactual decisions under δ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi &= E[\pi(\delta, y) - \pi(\delta^j, y)] \\ &= \alpha E[y(\delta - \delta^j)] - \beta E[\delta - \delta^j]. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

We cannot determine the prescription rule that achieves maximum Π without knowing the preference weights α and β . However, we can evaluate prescription rules that guarantee $\Pi > 0$ for any set of weights (Chalfin et al., 2016; Kleinberg et al., 2018). One rule maximizes the reduction in total antibiotic prescriptions, increasing the term $-\beta E[\delta - \delta^j]$ in Eq. (2) while imposing that prescriptions against bacterial infections remain unchanged, which ensures the term $\alpha E[y(\delta - \delta^j)]$ in Eq. (2) is zero. We examine prediction-based decision rules as functions of machine learning predicted risk $m(x)$ for a vector of predictors x and risk threshold $k \in [0, 1]$:

$$\delta(m(x); k) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m(x) < k, \\ 1 & \text{if } k \leq m(x). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The prescription decision for patient i is $d_i = \delta(m(x_i); k)$. We search k that maximizes Π given the constraint $\alpha E[y(\delta - \delta^j)] = 0$.

2.3. Medical and administrative data

Coherent unique personal identifiers enable us to merge administrative data with individual laboratory test results acquired from the clinical microbiological laboratories at Herlev hospital and Hvidovre hospital for the period between January 1, 2010, and December 31, 2012. These two hospitals serve all primary care clinics in Denmark's capital region accommodating 1.7 million citizens, around one third of the Danish population. Laboratory test results include rejection or confirmation of bacterial presence in a sample, resistance profiles, the date of sample acquisition, and the date results were reported to physicians.

Our administrative data cover all citizens in Denmark between January 1, 2002, and December 31, 2012. Registers are linked via unique patient (*Det Centrale Personregister, CPR*) and primary care clinic identifiers (*Yderregister, YDER*). The central personal registry contains socioeconomic and demographic variables. We obtain further background information from employment (*Integreerede Database for Arbejdsmarkedsforskning, IDA*) and education (*Uddannelseregister, UDDA*) registries. For each individual, the complete antibiotics purchase history (*Lægemiddeldatabasen, LMDB*), hospitalizations including ambulatory visits (*Landspatientregisteret, LPR*), and primary care insurance claims (*Sygesikringsregisteret, SSR*) are observable.

We split these data into segments of predictor variables according to their data sources. Table 1 reports the resulting segments *time and location, basic demographics, advanced demographics, health, and physician decisions*.

Primary care clinics and hospitals submitted 2,579,617 samples for testing from 2010 to 2012. Of 477,609 urine samples, 156,694 were submitted in primary care. We keep 148,300 observations with non-missing primary care clinic identifiers. We focus on initial consultations, excluding treatment spells if patients were tested or had received an antibiotic prescription within 4 weeks prior to the observation date, leaving 82,962 observations. We exclude 10,277 observations from pregnant patients for whom specific diagnostic and treatment guidelines apply. The resulting sample comprises 72,685 initial consultations from which a sample was sent to a laboratory.

We use 19,466 observations in 2010 exclusively for tuning and training. The remaining 23,351 and 29,868 observations, for 2011 and 2012, constitute our out of sample prediction sets, see Table S.1 in the supplementary material.

Table 1
Predictor variables, data segments, and required databases.

Data segments and variables	Databases ^a							
	LAB	CPR	IDA	UDDA	YDER	LMDB	SSR	LPR
1 Time and location								
Time ^b	✓							
Municipality		✓						
2 Basic demographics								
Age		✓						
Sex		✓						
3 Advanced demographics								
Civil status		✓						
Family type		✓						
Living constellation		✓						
Migration background		✓						
Origin country		✓						
Employment status			✓					
Occupation			✓					
Industry			✓					
Income			✓					
Highest educational degree				✓				
4 Health								
Antibiotic prescriptions ^c						✓		
Antibiotic resistance tests ^d	✓							
Hospitalizations ^e							✓	
Claims ^f								✓
Clinic identifier					✓			
Clinic-level testing ^g	✓				✓			
Municipality-level prescribing ^h		✓				✓		
5 Physician decisions								
Instantaneous prescription					✓	✓		
Molecule					✓	✓		
Volume					✓	✓		

^aLAB: laboratory test data, CPR: population data, IDA: employment data, UDDA: education data, YDER: physician identifiers, LMDB: prescriptions data, SSR: claims data, LPR: hospitalization data.

^bTime: Weekday, Week, Month, Quarter, School holidays.

^cAntibiotic prescriptions: Molecule, Volume, Indication, Number of days until current test; for patient's past 30 prescriptions.

^dAntibiotic resistance tests: Species, Resistances, Number of days to current test; for patient's past 5 tests.

^eHospitalizations: Length of stay, Diagnoses, Patient type, Number of days to current test; for patient's past 30 hospitalizations.

^fClaims: Procedure code and Number of weeks until current test, separated by general practitioners and specialists; for patient's past 30 claims.

^gClinic-level testing: Number of antibiotic resistance tests, Bacterial test rate; separated over all previous, past 1, past 3, past 6, and past 12 months, at clinic.

^hMunicipality-level prescribing: Daily Define Dose per inhabitant over past three months.

3. Results

3.1. Prediction and policy improvements

The out-of-sample prediction quality measured by AUC ranges from 0.686 (95% CI = 0.681–0.69) for the smallest set of predictor variables (segment 5) to 0.783 (95% CI = 0.779–0.787) for the combination of all data segments (Fig. 1, panel A).¹ AUC increases with additional data segments even though adding some segments results in insignificant increases. The largest increase in AUC appears from including patients' age and gender (segment 2) and the second largest when health information (segment 4) are added.

Counterfactual policy outcomes under a prediction-based rule are reported as the percentage reduction in antibiotic use relative to observed physician decisions, $(\delta(m(x); k) - \delta^j) / \delta^j$ (Fig. 1, panel B). Using only physicians' initial prescription decisions as predictors reduces antibiotic use by 0.66% (95% CI = 0.28–1.05). Adding time and location information (segment 1) improves policy outcomes slightly, whereas antibiotic use can be decreased

by 4.96% (95% CI = 4.35–5.58) by adding age and gender (segment 2) as predictors. Advanced demographics (segment 3) do not improve policy outcomes significantly. We find the largest improvement from adding health data (segment 4). With all data combined, antibiotic use can be reduced by 9.32% (95% CI = 8.54–10) without treating fewer bacterial infections.

3.2. Comparison

Panel C in Fig. 1 shows the value of an additional data segment, computed as the difference between two subsequent segments relative to the difference obtained from using the complete data (all segments) and the smallest data combination (segment 5).

Adding time and location information (segment 1) improves policy outcomes to a similar degree as prediction quality. However, adding the simple patient characteristics of age and gender (segment 2) results in a markedly larger increase in prediction quality than policy improvements. Age and gender are informative for prediction quality but also easily observed by physicians against whose treatment decisions we evaluate policy improvements.

¹ 95% confidence intervals are computed based on 1,000 bootstrap samples.

Fig. 1. Prediction and prescription policy results.

Advanced demographics (segment 3) account for similarly small shares of attainable improvements. The addition of rich health care data (segment 4) results in a smaller value added for prediction quality compared to policy improvements. Data that may be more difficult to observe and analyze for physicians are likely to be the most useful for improving decision-making.

4. Discussion

Identifying data needs for prediction policy problems poses a practical challenge: Which subset of costly and diverse data is required to make an implementation worthwhile? The findings in our study provide a general insight on the value of additional data. While more data lead to better prediction quality and reduced antibiotic use, the origins of improvements vary. The scope for policies to improve upon human decisions depends crucially on whether an algorithm enables predictions that employ information beyond what decision makers already know. Therefore, evaluating policy potential based on prediction quality can be misleading. The value of increasingly rich data combinations must be quantified by evaluating predictions relative to human decisions, which depend on the quality of human experts' risk assessment and their objectives.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2022.110360>.

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